

Farmers' Awareness, Practice, Challenges, And Regulatory Needs on Foliar Fertilisers in Tomato Farming in Tanzania

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ABSTRACT

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Tomato is the most important vegetable crop in Tanzania; however, its productivity remains low, primarily due to poor soil fertility and limited use and access to quality agricultural inputs. In recent years, there has been a growing shift toward the use of foliar fertilisers (FF), which are designed to promote rapid nutrient uptake as complementary inputs to soil fertilisation. Although FF products are considered to have great potential, information on farmers' awareness, usage, and perceptions particularly among smallholders remains limited. This study assessed farmers' knowledge, practices, and attitudes toward foliar fertilisers in Kalenga, Ibangamoyo and Mgera villages in Iringa – Tanzania. The study employed a cross-sectional mixed-methods design and data were collected by structured questionnaires, focus group discussions and key informant interviews. Results revealed high awareness (96%) and basic understanding (93%) of foliar fertilisers among smallholder farmers; however, only 28% were confident in their application. A substantial proportion of farmers (43.5%) reported poor efficacy of certain foliar fertilisers, with Super Gro and Victory Booster most frequently identified as less effective. Despite these concerns, no formal complaints were submitted to regulatory authorities. This was largely attributed to limited awareness of reporting procedures, fear of potential repercussions, and a low level of trust in regulatory institutions. Farmers recommended stronger quality control (87.5%), unannounced inspections (76.2%) and digital traceability (66.7%). The study showed a disconnect between product availability and quality assurance, calling for the urgent need for farmer training, market regulation, and improved monitoring systems to ensure safe and effective foliar fertiliser use in Tanzania.

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INTRODUCTION

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) is a commonly grown vegetable crop worldwide, with an estimated production of 189 metric tonnes, with China having the largest share of 35% (Govindasamy et al., 2023). The crop is popular in Tanzania as it contributes to increased income for smallholder farmers and nutrition, as it provides vitamins and minerals (Bwade et al., 2025). Despite the importance of tomatoes in Tanzania the average productivity is quite low with less than 13 tonnes per hectare compared to the global average of 36 tonnes per hectare (Singh et al., 2025). The major limiting factors include poor soil fertility, poor agronomic practices and limited use and access to quality agricultural inputs (FAO, 2020; Stewart et al., 2020). To address nutrient gaps, smallholder farmers have been using conventional methods, particularly granular fertilisers. However, due to the recent technological advancement, there has been growing awareness of using foliar fertilisers as a complementary input. Foliar fertilisers are applied directly to plant leaves, where nutrients are rapidly absorbed through the cuticles and stomata (Fernández and Eichert, 2009; Zhang and Brown, 1999). They are also known to be effective in correcting micronutrient deficiencies, enhancing crop physiological responses during stress, and improving resistance to pests and diseases (Murtaza et al., 2022). However, information on how these foliar fertilisers are perceived, understood and applied by vegetable growers in Tanzania is scarce. In addition, concerns have been raised about the spread of less effective, mislabelled, expired, or adulterated foliar fertilisers in the Tanzanian agro-input market. Understanding these aspects is essential for farmers, agro-input suppliers, and extension officers, as well as for strengthening regulatory oversight, ensuring market transparency, and guiding policies that enhance input-use efficiency, boost yields, and promote sustainable development in the vegetable subsector. It was envisaged that this study would also align with the recent policy discussions in Tanzania which have called for stronger collaboration between regulatory authorities, agro-dealers, and extension services to address potential non-compliance and safeguard farmers' trust in emerging agro-input technologies. Therefore, this study aimed to bridge the gaps by assessing smallholder tomato producers' knowledge, practices, and challenges related to product efficacy, quality control, and advisory services, with the intention of informing both farmer support programs and policy-level discussions on improving fertiliser input systems in Tanzania.

MATERIALS and METHODS

Ethical Statement

This study obtained research clearance from The Open University of Tanzania (2025) (Ref. No: OUT/PG20241882).

Study Design

The study used a cross-sectional descriptive design to evaluate smallholder tomato farmers' knowledge, practices and challenges related to product efficacy, quality control, and advisory services regarding foliar fertiliser use. Both quantitative and qualitative methods were integrated in a mixed-methods framework, which allowed for triangulation of outcomes and a comprehensive understanding of farmers' behaviour and limitations.

Study Area

The study was conducted in Kalenga, Ibangamoyo and Mgera villages, located in Iringa District, Iringa region-in southern highlands of Tanzania (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A map of Tanzania showing the location of the study sites (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022)

The three villages were purposively selected due to their importance in tomato production, the availability of different farming systems such as rain-fed, irrigated, and greenhouse systems. In addition, Iringa region is among the leading horticultural production zones in Tanzania, with significant contributions to national tomato production.

Target Population and Sampling Procedure

The study targeted primary stakeholder groups, namely, small- and medium-scale tomato farmers; extension officers; and agro-input suppliers. These stakeholders were considered crucial in both the tomato and inputs value chains, particularly in influencing adoption and effective use of agricultural technologies such as foliar fertilisers. A mixed sampling strategy was employed, incorporating both random and purposive techniques to ensure broad and representative data collection across tomato-growing farmers.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size for farmer interviews was determined using Yamane's formula (Yamane, 1973) as cited by Oluigbo *et al.* (2024), which is appropriate for finite populations when the level of precision is known:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \quad (1)$$

Where: n = size of sample, N = total population size of farmers in the sites, e = the required margin of error (0.05).

Following the above formula, the number of farmers interviewed was determined as shown below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{100}{1 + 100(0.05)^2} = 80$$

Thus, eighty (80) small - and medium-scale tomato farmers in three villages (Kalenga 32, Ibangamoyo 24 and Mgera 24) were selected. The sampling frame was developed in collaboration with village agricultural extension officers, ensuring that all eligible tomato farmers had an equal chance of being selected through simple random sampling.

Sampling of Participants for Focus Group Discussion and Key Informant Interviews

In each village, two Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) were steered, with each group comprising 8 - 12 participants. Participants were selected to represent diversity in gender, age, farm size, and experience with foliar fertilisers. Participants for Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) were purposively selected based on their specialised knowledge or strategic roles within the tomato value chain. These included extension officers, agro-dealers, and village leaders who were well-positioned to provide in-depth views on topics such as adoption patterns, usage practices and challenges associated with foliar fertilisers in tomato production.

Data Collection

Interview by Structured Questionnaire

Interviews were carried out using a structured interviewer-administered questionnaire which contained both closed- and open-ended questions. The questionnaire was designed based on the Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices (KAP) in agricultural innovations perspective and aligned with study objectives.

Focus Group Discussions

The FGDs explored collective practices and perceptions about foliar fertiliser use. The FGDs enabled the researchers to capture broad information on community knowledge, shared perceptions, and collective practices relevant to foliar fertiliser use in those study sites. Discussions tracked a guide with key thematic areas like attitudes towards foliar fertilisers application stages, challenges on misuse of foliar fertiliser and suggestions for improving product quality. Each session was audio-recorded after seeking consent from the participants and later transcribed for thematic analysis.

Key Informant Interviews

Twelve key informant interviews (KIIs) were conducted. The KIIs gathered expert opinion from extension officers and agro dealers, where a semi-structured checklist was used, focusing on farmer advisory services and complaints/concerns, input supply trends, extension gaps, observed effects of foliar products on plant growth and the yield and effectiveness of fertiliser regulatory support.

Data Analysis

Data from questionnaire interviews were coded and analysed using R Statistical Software (v4.6.0). The analysis included descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages to summarise key variables, cross-tabulations and Chi-square tests to assess associations between demographic factors and foliar fertiliser use. Data obtained from FGDs and KIIs were subjected to thematic content analysis. Triangulation of data from interviews, FGDs, and KIIs enhanced the validity and robustness of the findings.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic and Farm Profile of Farmers

Age Distribution

Among the tomato farmers who participated in the survey, 72.5% were male and their ages ranged from 20 to 69. The number of farmers differed significantly among the six age categories ($\chi^2 = 26.65$, $P < 0.001$) where 26 farmers in the age category of 30 - 39 was significantly higher than those in the age group of 60 and above (9 farmers) ($P < 0.040$) and under 20 age groups (2 farmers) ($P < 0.003$). Likewise, the age category of 40 - 49 had a significantly higher number of farmers (17 farmers) than those under the 20-age category (2 farmers) ($P < 0.040$). The significant difference in age distribution among smallholder tomato farmers might be influencing the number of individuals who are engaged in tomato production. These findings conform to previous studies by Ochieng et al. (2022) which indicated that demographic factors, mainly the age play a critical role in farming arrangement and decision-making. The observed dominance of farmers in the 30-39 and 40-49 age categories implies that tomato agribusiness is most actively done by middle-aged adults. These results align with studies done by Onyancha (2024), who reported that the middle-aged persons in sub-Saharan Africa were often the most economically active and physically capable of engaging in rigorous agricultural practices such as vegetable business. On the other hand, youth (under 20) and elderly farmers (60+) appeared understated, mainly due to the number of challenges such as limited land accessibility and or capital, and physical ability for elders. On the other hand, elderly individuals may be scaling back physical labour or transitioning to supervisory roles in family farming enterprises as observed by Msengi and Akyoo (2023).

Educational Level

Significant difference was noted in the education levels among farmers ($\chi^2 = 49.63$, $P < 0.001$) across the three study sites (Kalenga, Ibangamoyo, and Mgera). Thirty-seven (37) farmers with primary education accounted for 44% of the respondents and significantly differed from the rest of the group categories, followed by secondary education (31%) and the last category was vocational/tertiary educational (3%). However, there were no statistically significant association between education level and study sites implying that education levels among farmers did not differ significantly in the three sites. The observed proportion of farmers with higher level of education particularly those with vocational and tertiary training may be better equipped to understand agronomic recommendations, interpret requirements on the product as per labels, and adopt improved agricultural technologies such as foliar fertiliser or integrated pest management (IPM). These findings corroborate previous studies that highlight education

as a critical determinant of the adoption of agricultural practices, productivity, and market participation (Mignouna et al., 2011). This is essential as education enhances access to extension services, record keeping, and financial literacy, which are vital to profitability in commercial tomato farming (Wossen et al., 2017). On the other hand, the limited formal education may limit a farmer’s ability to realise and apply the recommended practices which leads to suboptimal farm practices as also suggested by URT (2022).

Years of Experience, Land Used in Tomato Farming and Farming Practices

This study noted that most of the interviewed farmers have worked on tomato farming production for 6 to 10 years (Figure 2), and their experience in tomato farming differed significantly ($\chi^2 = 11.8$; $P < 0.008$).

Figure 2. Tomato farming experience in the study area

However, the association of farming experience and study sites was not statistically significant indicating that no meaningful difference in number of farmers between the sites. Regarding the average size of land used in tomato production, the land units ranged from 0.5 to 1 hectare which differed significantly among farmers ($\chi^2 = 21.50$; $P < 0.001$). Significant differences ($\chi^2 = 84.30$; $P < 0.001$) were further observed among the farmers in the study sites in their farming practices i.e rainfed, irrigated and screenhouse, with irrigation farming being predominant (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Farming practices distribution in the study area

Similar observations on farming experience were made in Ethiopia by Teklewold et al. (2013) who noted that farming experience helps farmers to go deeper in understanding cropping systems, weather variability, and market behaviour which shape adoption of agricultural innovations, productivity, and farm management competence. In contrast, new players in tomato farming especially those with less than three years of experience might have been hindered by lack of knowledge, limited capital, and weaker access to extension services as suggested by Langyintuo (2020). On the other hand, the observed significant difference in land size suggests substantial variation in farmer numbers across different landholding categories. These patterns align with broader findings across sub-Saharan Africa, where landholding size is strongly correlated with the scale and intensity of agricultural production (Chamberlin and Jayne, 2019). The significantly lower participation in screen house farming may be attributed to its high initial investment costs, technical knowledge requirements, and limited access to materials such as greenhouse plastic or drip irrigation kits barriers particularly prevalent in rural Tanzania (Mhoru et al., 2023).

Awareness and Knowledge of Foliar Fertilisers

Foliar Fertiliser Awareness and Duration of Use

The study revealed that out of 80 respondents, 96% reported having heard of foliar fertilisers. Among those who are aware, 12% first heard about foliar fertilisers within the last year, 18% between 1 and 3 years ago, and 70% more than 3 years ago. The findings

also revealed that influential sources of agricultural information for vegetable growers were agricultural suppliers (29%), extension officers (23%), and peer farmers (23%), while online sources were the least utilized. However, in the “other category”, radio, home television, school curriculum and workshop/seminars, were mentioned. The findings indicate a high level of awareness of foliar fertilisers among farmers among farmers which aligns with previous research that indicated the tendency of experienced farmers to adopt foliar fertilisers earlier compared to the rest of the category as observed by Serote, (2021). The statistically significant effect of duration of involvement in tomato farming on the number of farmers show that farmer experience influences foliar fertiliser awareness levels. These findings align with earlier studies that suggested that adoption of agricultural technologies is typically driven more by individual farmer characteristics such as experience, education, and access to training than by location-specific factors (Tambo and Abdoulaye, 2012; Quinhentos, 2017). In addition, the significantly higher proportion of farmers who had been growing tomatoes for more than three years, compared with those with 1–3 years of experience and those with less than one year of experience, suggests that most of the farmers assessed were long-term tomato producers, while new entrants remained relatively few. These demographic trends may reflect structural entry barriers such as limited access to land, capital, and knowledge among prospective or younger farmers (IFAD, 2019).

Foliar Fertiliser Products Commonly Used

There were several brands of inorganic foliar fertilisers that were mostly used by farmers (Table 1). Green Gold had the highest frequency (24%) in use, followed by Super Gro (17%), Mo-Quick Booster (16%), and New Victory Booster (12%). Products like Super Feed, Mazao Booster, Starter Growth, NPK Booster and Goldfert had relatively low usage across sites. Kalenga exhibited high usage of Super Gro and Mo-Quick Booster, while Green Gold was most frequently used in Ibangamoyo, and New Victory Booster and Green Gold were prominent in Mgera. It was evident that the usage of these foliar fertiliser products was statistically significant among the sites ($X^2 = 37.75$, $P < 0.001$). However, neither foliar organic nor bio-fertiliser brands were mentioned during the survey.

Table 1. List of foliar fertilisers mostly used by farmers in Kalenga, Ibangamoyo and Mgera sites

Trade name	Nutrient composition	Company	Year of registration	Registration number
Goldfert	10%N: 50%P ₂ O ₅ : 10%K ₂ O	Agrimatco Tanzania limited	2017	217
Green Gold	33% N	ETG Inputs Limited	2018	172
Mazao booster	32%N: 10%P ₂ O ₅ : 20%K ₂ O + 20%S, 2%B 2%Zn, 2.8%Fe, 3.7%Cu, 2.7%Mn, 2%Mo, 2.8%Co	Meru Seed Company Limited	2020	310
Mo-Quick booster	20%N: 20%P ₂ O ₅ : 20%K ₂ O	Amka Feeders Limited	2018	175
New Victory booster	19%N: 19%P ₂ O ₅ : 10%K ₂ O	Mtali Agrotraders Co. Ltd	2020	330
NPK booster	14%N: 14%P ₂ O ₅ : 20%K ₂ O + MgO, 0.1% B	Tanzania Crop Care Limited	2013	81
Starter Growth	15 %N: 30 %P ₂ O ₅ : 15 %K ₂ O + 15 ppmB, 400 ppmZn, 400 ppmFe, 50 ppmCu, 300 ppmMn.	Evayla General Trading Co. Ltd	2022	485
Super feed	19%N: 19%P ₂ O ₅ : 19%K ₂ O + Mg + TE	Agrifarmers center	2020	317
Super gro	7.5%N: 4.7%P: 3.3%K+ 0.1%Zn,0.8%Ca	Neolife International Limited	2024	FERT/11-1919
Yaravita Crop boost	0%N: 30%P ₂ O ₅ : 5%K ₂ O + 2.5%Mg + 3.1%Zn	Yara Tanzania Limited	2020	111

The usage trends suggest that farmer preferences are mostly influenced by several factors including product availability, the perceived effectiveness, affordability, and marketing efforts by mainly agro-dealers or extension officers as previously suggested by Sheahan et al. (2014). The observed significant effect of product type on usage frequency associates with adoption studies indicating that farmers' input choices are influenced more by perceived efficacy and prior experience than by geographical location (Klitgaard, 2020). The relative superiority of Green Gold product may be attributed to the effective product positioning or superior yield outcomes, reinforcing the notion that farmers rely on trial-and-error and peer recommendations when evaluating agro-inputs (Isakson, 2015).

Combination of Foliar fertilisers with Other Agrochemicals

Thirty three percent (33%) of farmers reported mixing foliar fertilisers with pesticides during application. Most common combinations included foliar fertilisers with other foliar fertilisers (52%), foliar fertilisers with insecticides (26%) and foliar fertiliser with insecticides and herbicides (22%). Only 7% reported issues such as leaf burn or reduced efficacy particularly when high dosages were used, while 89% believed foliar fertilisers contributed to improving plant health and pest resistance. Farmers noted some pests and diseases that were less severe when tank mixes were used included tomato mosaic virus (ToMV) (31%), leaf miners (*Tuta absoluta*) (25%), early blight (*Alternaria solani*) (19%), septonia leaf spot (*Septoria lycopersici*) (14%), and powdery mildew (*Oidium lycopersici*) (11%). The reported increased use of tank mixture of foliar fertilisers with other agrochemical inputs is consistent with integrated crop management strategies that aim at enhancing efficiency and reducing labour inputs. In this case, this observation corroborates with previous reports suggesting that farmers know the operational and economic benefits of combined applications which include saving time (Gandini et al., 2020). The lack of significant variation in frequency of use across different input combinations or study sites may reflect a relatively uniform adoption pattern of foliar fertiliser-agrochemical mixtures across Kalenga, Ibangamoyo, and Mgera. This might have been influenced by common extension advice or agro-dealer recommendations. Similar studies have noted that farmers' decisions on foliar fertiliser combinations are not strongly site-dependent, but rather guided by availability, cost, or convenience (Aker, 2011; Feder et al., 2004). Importantly, the adverse effect of foliar fertilisers, noted by 7% of farmers, such as phytotoxicity in the form of leaf burn, or reduced efficacy associated with mixing foliar fertilisers and other agrochemicals may be attributed to inappropriate practices in timing and dosage or could indicate limited awareness of potential incompatibilities (Fernández and Brown, 2013). The study revealed that the majority (89%) of farmers observed that foliar fertilisers contributed to improved plant health and enhanced pest resistance. This aligns with several previous reports that noted that foliar nutrition

strengthens plant physiological resilience, enhances disease resistance, and improves tolerance to biotic factors (Dass et al., 2022). Micronutrients such as zinc, manganese, and copper delivered through the foliage are known to activate enzymes and pathways that mitigate fungal and viral infections (Kuyper, 2012).

Perceived Quality, Labelling Issues, and Regulatory Gaps in Foliar Fertiliser Use

Experiences with less Effective or Poor-performing Foliar Fertilisers

It was observed that 43.5% reported using foliar fertilisers did not deliver the expected results in the field. The brands that were mentioned frequently for not performing properly included Super Grow, Victory Booster, Mazao Booster (NPK), Kijani Booster, Kyto Booster, Mafanikio Booster, and Biogenic. In fact, the recurrent mentioning of Victory Booster across villages suggests widespread farmer dissatisfaction and heightened scrutiny of its performance. Incidentally, some respondents were unable to recall the exact names but acknowledged the presence of multiple ineffective products in the market. The reported presence of foliar fertilisers in the market that were not performing as expected raises important concerns regarding product efficacy, usage and the effectiveness of regulation and monitoring of foliar fertilisers in Tanzania. Similar issues have been documented in other sub-Saharan African countries, where the proliferation of unregulated or substandard agro inputs has negatively impacted farmer trust and productivity (Van Campenhout et al., 2021). Additionally, the poor performance of some foliar fertilisers could be attributed to multiple factors, including improper formulation, falsified labels, poor manufacturing practices, or lack of proper storage and handling protocols in the distribution chain (Aung et al., 2014). Moreover, the lack of systematic product verification or post-market surveillance exacerbates the issue, allowing such products to circulate widely without accountability (Spielman and Kennedy, 2016).

Farmer Criteria for Selecting Foliar Fertilisers

Farmers revealed several criteria when purchasing or applying foliar fertilisers. These included nutrient composition and formulation (95.2%) indicating that the type and ratio of nutrients were their top consideration. Additionally, 90.5% of farmers reported closely reviewing labels for information such as expiry and manufacture dates and instructions for dosage and mode of use. However, few of them noted the importance of label clarity and the use of Kiswahili language for ease of understanding while others complained about difficult-to-read or incomplete labels. Regulatory approval (42.9%), peer recommendations and prior experience (38.1%) and product safety and compatibility (28.6%) were added criteria to assess whether the product was safe for use on tomatoes, safe for the user, and whether it dissolved well in water and could be used in spraying equipment such as knapsack sprayers. The considerable discretion of

farmers prioritising nutrient composition and formulation, aligns with previous studies which noted that farmers prefer products based on nutrient composition due to their direct impact on plant growth and productivity (Biru et al., 2025). The reported focus on scrutiny of manufacturing and expiry dates is encouraging as it indicates that farmers are aware of potential efficacy loss over time, a concern noted by regulatory authorities and agronomists (Onyancha, 2024). However, the fact that only 42.9% of farmers reported actively checking for authority registration numbers indicates a significant regulatory communication gap. This gap might contribute to the proliferation of substandard or counterfeit products in rural markets as observed by Bumb et al. (2021). The concern over poor product label readability - particularly labels written in English, printed in small font sizes, and lacking translation into Kiswahili - represents a significant barrier to informed decision-making, potentially reducing the usability and safety of agro-inputs, as observed in previous studies conducted in Tanzania and elsewhere (Sheahan et al., 2017; Massomo, 2019). The noted reliance of farmers on recommendations and information from peers (38.1%) on the usage of foliar fertilisers reflects broader trends in sub-Saharan Africa, where farmers trust interpersonal communication and experiential knowledge more than official advisories when adopting new technologies (Muoni et al., 2019).

Reasons for Poor Efficacy of Foliar Fertilisers Compared to Soil Fertilisers

Farmers revealed several reasons contributing to poor efficacy of foliar fertilisers including low concentrations of nutrients which accounted for 71.4% of respondents, incorrect dosage, mixing foliar fertilisers with inappropriate chemicals, or using dirty water (66.7), lack of farmer awareness on application timing, mixing, and target crop stage which leads to misuse (61.9%). Other reasons were mislabelling, counterfeit products, or inconsistent formulations (57.1%), biological limitations of foliar feeding (38.1%), poor timing (e.g., spraying during extreme heat or dryness) or unfavourable weather conditions reduce uptake and efficacy (28.6%) and storage and failure to observe shelf lives (19%). The concerns of surveyed farmers on the poor performance of some foliar fertilisers aligns with previous studies which pointed out that the presence of adulterated or improperly formulated foliar products on the market, often fail to meet the declared nutrient specifications (Bumb et al., 2021). The incorrect application practices including incorrect dosage, and the use of contaminated products might reflect broader gaps in farmer training and knowledge transfer systems in rural areas. These observations align with the studies of Enwerem et al. (2022) who noted that without clear and practical guidance, smallholder farmers are prone to experiment with mixing inputs in ways that may compromise their efficacy or even harm the crop. Unfriendly weather conditions and inappropriate spraying times noted under this study might significantly reduce leaf uptake and even cause leaf burn, rendering foliar applications ineffective or phytotoxic as also observed by Biru et al.

(2025). Finally, concerns about shelf life and improper storage underline the need for proper input management both at retail and farm levels as exposure to heat or prolonged opening of containers can degrade nutrients or destabilize formulations (Onyancha, 2024).

Reporting of Poor-Quality Foliar Fertilisers to Authorities

During the study, it was found that all the respondents (100%) had never reported any foliar fertiliser suspected to be substandard, fake, or underperforming to any government institution or regulatory authority. Reasons for this was the lack of awareness, where 76.2% of farmers were unsure about how, where, or to whom they had to report such issues. Doubt about the effectiveness of reporting was the second most cited reason, with 52.4% of farmers expressing scepticism that reporting would lead to any meaningful action or change, often citing past experiences or hearsay. Fear of potential disputes with agro dealers was mentioned by 38.1% of farmers, particularly in tightly knit rural communities. In addition, 33.3% of farmers reported a general lack of trust in regulatory institutions, expressing little faith in formal follow-ups or inspections and believing that their complaints would not be taken seriously or acted upon. The complete lack of reporting of alleged substandard or underperforming foliar fertilisers might indicate presence of systemic breakdown in the feedback and enforcement loop within the fertiliser regulatory framework in Tanzania. The lack of awareness on where or how to report such issue(s) confirms previous studies showing that awareness on roles of regulatory institutions like the Tanzania Fertilizer Regulatory Authority (TFRA) remains limited among rural smallholders (Bumb et al., 2021). Fear of interpersonal conflict with local agro dealers especially in rural communities might indicate that social relationships are vital, so reporting a seller for a suspected fake or poor-quality product could result in community tension or ostracism. This social barrier has also been identified in other agricultural contexts, where farmers avoid whistleblowing to preserve business relationships or personal safety (Vaidya et al., 2023). Finally, a lack of trust in regulatory bodies might stem previous encounters, observed inefficiencies, or general dissatisfaction with the responsiveness of such institutions as also noted by Jayne et al. (2018).

Farmer Recommendations for Regulatory Authorities

It was noted that 87.5% of farmers emphasised the need for strengthened quality control and proper registration processes before foliar fertilisers are marketed. In addition, 76.2% of respondents recommended regular product surveillance of fertiliser dealers and manufacturers to eliminate counterfeit or substandard products. Other recommendations from respondents included enforcement of digital traceability system (66.7%) to ensure foliar fertilisers products are trackable from production to

farm gate, proper labelling and language clarity (61.9%) using Kiswahili language, capacity building and farmer education (57.1%) importation/local manufacturing to be seasonally coordinated and regulated (47.6%), total ban or blacklisting of substandard fertilisers (42.9%) and the introduction of subsidy and price controls for genuine foliar fertilisers (14.3%). The strong recommendation on strengthening quality control and registration processes echoes global calls for evidence-based registration procedures, especially in regions where substandard or counterfeit agro-inputs are prevalent (Spielman and Smale, 2017). Internationally, regulatory frameworks such as those in the European Union and COMESA have been pointing up risk-based tiered testing, harmonisation, and digital transparency (Sundaramoorthy and Jaiganesh, 2025). These standards rationalise approvals, reduce duplication, and allow mutual recognition of foreign trial data, thereby lowering costs and accelerating access to authentic products. Given recent reports of less effective foliar fertiliser products in the Tanzanian market, such a process would not only safeguard farmers' investment but also help preserve trust in emerging agro technologies. The unannounced market surveillance and enforcement of fertiliser dealers shows how vitality are, for uncovering non-compliance and removing substandard or expired products from the supply chain. The introduction of digital traceability system, such as the use of QR codes and product lot numbers reflects a growing recognition among farmers of the role that digital technologies can play part in enhancing fertiliser traceability and accountability. It has been noted in some African countries particularly Nigeria (through Visualizing Insights on Fertilizer for African Agriculture (VIFAA) program and National Digital Farmers Registry (NDFR)) and Kenya (through Kenya Integrated Agriculture Management Information System (KIAMIS)), that digital fertiliser authentication systems significantly reduce the circulation of counterfeit products and promote regulatory transparency (Ali, 2021). The need for capacity building and farmer education concurs with recommendations from previous studies of Van Campenhout et al. (2021) that noted training programs significantly enhanced the adoption and correct usage of inputs, resulting in improved yields and reduced risk of misuse.

CONCLUSION and RECOMENDATION

The study has highlighted the influence of education, farming experience, land size, and farming systems on the awareness and adoption of foliar fertilisers. Although farmers demonstrated a good conceptual understanding particularly on rapid nutrient uptake and stress tolerance benefits of foliar fertilisers, a significant gap still exists between theoretical understanding and practical application, with only 28% of farmers reporting high confidence in correct usage. The noted comparatively low adoption rate of foliar fertilisers despite its growing availability in the market calls for strengthened extension services and farmer training programs. Cautiously, not a single farmer

reported substandard fertiliser products to authorities, and this alerts a critical weakness in the current feedback and enforcement systems. Therefore, policy recommendations for TFRA must move further by including concrete implementation steps such as operationalising a national digital traceability system via mobile authentication platforms, establishing anonymous reporting channels to protect farmer identity, and launching public awareness campaigns to close the reporting gap. Moreover, urgent regulatory reforms including strict product registration protocols, mandated use of bilingual (English and Kiswahili) labelling. Research should focus on verifying the nutrient content and field efficacy of commonly used foliar fertilisers, as well as their economic benefits for smallholders. In doing so, Tanzania can boost farmer confidence, reduce counterfeit circulation, and align its fertiliser governance with international best practices.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Authors Contributions

SMSM and ENK contributed to the project idea, study design, and execution. LMR conducted the surveys and wrote the first draft of the manuscript.

REFERENCES

- Aker JC., 2011. Dial "A" for agriculture: a review of information and communication technologies for agricultural extension in developing countries. *Agricultural Economics*, 42(6): 631–647.
- Ali M., 2021. Mobile technology use by rural farmers and herders. Walden University (Doctoral dissertation).
- Aung MM., Chang YS, 2014. Traceability in a food supply chain: safety and quality perspectives. *Food Control*, 39: 172–184.
- Biru H, Tassie K, Endalew B., 2025. Does irrigation improve smallholders' vegetable intake and diet quality? Evidence from Northwest Ethiopia. *International Journal of Vegetable Science*, 1–38.
- Bumb BL, Ariga J, Anand M, Cameron A, Nkonya NM., 2021. Assessment of the fertilizer market and bulk procurement system in the United Republic of Tanzania: policy report. Food and Agriculture Organization.

Bwade EK, Aliyu B, Tashiwa YI., 2025. Preservation of fresh tomatoes using biochemical treatments: a systematic review. *Agricultural Engineering International: CIGR Journal*, 27(3): 208–222.

Chamberlin J, Jayne T., 2019. Unpacking the meaning of “market access”. *Gates Open Research*, 3: 791.

Dass A, Rajanna GA, Babu S, Lal SK, Choudhary AK, Singh R, Kumar B., 2022. Foliar application of macro- and micronutrients improves productivity and resource-use efficiency of soybean in a semiarid climate. *Sustainability*, 14(10): 5825.

Enwerem VA, Osuagwu OC, Okereke-Ejiogu E, Ajaero JO, Osugiri II, Ohajianya D., 2022. Effects of agricultural extension services on leaf vegetable farmers’ use of agro-chemicals in Imo State, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Agriculture and Food Sciences*, 10(4):47-54.

FAO., 2020. *The State of Food and Agriculture 2020: Overcoming water challenges in agriculture*. Rome: <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb1447en>

Feder G, Murgai R, Quizon JB., 2004. Sending farmers back to school: The impact of farmer field schools in Indonesia. *Review of Agricultural Economics*, 26(1): 45-62.

Fernández V, Brown PH., 2013. From plant surface to plant metabolism: the uncertain fate of foliar-applied nutrients. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 4: 289.

Fernández V, Eichert T., 2009. Uptake of hydrophilic solutes through plant leaves: current state of knowledge and perspectives of foliar fertilization. *Critical Reviews in Plant Sciences*, 28(1–2): 36–68.

Gandini EMM, Costa ESP, dos Santos JB, Soares MA, Barroso GM, Corrêa JM, Zanuncio JC., 2020. Compatibility of pesticides and/or fertilizers in tank mixtures. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 268: 122152.

Govindasamy R, Ceylan RF, Özkan B., 2025. Global tomato production: price sensitivity and policy impact in Mexico, Türkiye, and the United States. *Horticulturae*, 11(1): 84.

IFAD., 2019. *Creating opportunities for rural youth: 2019 rural development report*. IFAD., <https://www.ifad.org/en/web/knowledge/publication/asset/41173241>

Isakson SR., 2015. Derivatives for development? Small-farmer vulnerability and financialization of climate risk. *Journal of Agrarian Change*, 15(4): 569–580.

Jayne TS, Mason NM, Burke WJ, Ariga J, 2018. Africa’s second-generation agricultural input subsidy programs. *Food Policy*, 75: 1–14.

Klitgaard K., 2020. Sustainability as an economic issue: a biophysical perspective. *Sustainability*, 12(1): 364.

Kuyper TW., 2012. Ectomycorrhiza and the open nitrogen cycle in an afro-tropical rainforest. *New Phytologist*, 195(4): 728-729.

Langyintuo A., 2020. Smallholder farmers' access to inputs and finance in Africa. In *The role of smallholder farms in food and nutrition security* (pp. 133-152). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

Massomo SMS., 2019. Vegetable pest management and pesticide use in Kigoma Tanzania: challenges and way forward. *OUT Huria Journal*, 26(1): 195–227.

Mhoro L, Meya AI, Amuri NA, Ndakidemi PA, Mtei KM, Njau KN., 2023. Influence of farmers' socio-economic characteristics on nutrient flow and implications for system sustainability in smallholdings: a review. *Frontiers in Soil Science*, 3: 1112629.

Mignouna DB, Manyong VM, Rusike J, Mutabazi KDS, Senkondo EM., 2011. Determinants of adopting imazapyr-resistant maize technologies and its impact on household income in Western Kenya. *AgBioForum*, 14(3): 158-163.

Msengi DM, Akyoo A., 2023. The nexus between age groups, gender dynamics of smallholder maize farmers, and poverty status in Tanzania. *Global Social Welfare*, 1–12.

Muoni T, Barnes AP, Öborn I, Watson CA, Bergkvist G, Shiluli M, Duncan AJ., 2019. Farmer perceptions of legumes and their functions in smallholder farming systems in East Africa. *International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability*, 17(3): 205–218.

Murtaza DF, Roşculete E, Roşculete CA, Păunescu G., 2022. Foliar fertilization - an integral part of complex and integrated fertilizations: a review. *Annals of the University of Craiova*, 52(2): 100–107.

National Bureau of Statistics., 2022. Census Hub Tanzania. <https://sensa.nbs.go.tz/>

Ochieng J, Afari-Sefa V, Muthoni F, Kansiime M, Hoeschle-Zeledon I, Bekunda M, Thomas D., 2022. Adoption of sustainable agricultural technologies for vegetable production in rural Tanzania. *International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability*, 20(4): 478–496.

Oluigbo CU, Ngozi EC, Ohaegbu PMNI., 2024. Determination of sample sizes in research using Taro Yamane formula: An overview. In *Proceedings of the 1st Annual Faculty of Science International Conference*, Niger Delta University, Amassoma, Nigeria. pp. 14-16.

Onyancha EO., 2024. Effect of farmer's participation and perception of NGO interventions on household food security in Kenya (Doctoral dissertation, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology). Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology.

Quinhentos M., 2017. Social networks and farmers' willingness to adopt new agricultural technologies: The case of a new phosphorus-efficient bean variety in rural

Mozambique (Master's thesis, Pennsylvania State University). Pennsylvania State University.

Serote B, Mokgehle S, Du Plooy C, Mpandeli S, Nhamo L, Senyolo G., 2021. Factors influencing adoption of climate-smart irrigation technologies in arid areas of South Africa. *Agriculture*, 11(12): 1222.

Sheahan M, Barrett CB, Goldvale C., 2017. Human health and pesticide use in sub-Saharan Africa. *Agricultural Economics*, 48(S1): 27–41.

Sheahan M, Barrett CB., 2014. Understanding the agricultural input landscape in sub-Saharan Africa. World Bank Policy Research Working Paper 7014.

Singh S, Singh P, Singh G, Sandhu AS., 2025. Crop productivity and energy indices of tomato production under poly-house structures. *Energy*, 314: 134239.

Spielman DJ, Kennedy A., 2016. Towards better metrics and policymaking for seed system development. *Agricultural Systems*, 147: 111–122.

Spielman DJ, Smale M., 2017. Policy options to accelerate variety change among smallholder farmers in South Asia and Africa south of the Sahara (IFPRI Discussion Paper No. 01666). International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI). Pp:1-54.

Stewart ZP, Pierzynski GM, Middendorf BJ, Prasad PV., 2020. Approaches to improve soil fertility in sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 71(2): 632–641.

Sundaramoorthy S, Jaiganesh V., 2025. Policies, regulations and quality assurance requirements for sustainable agriculture. In Nagaraju D, Yanjarappa SM, Purushothama CRA (Eds.), *Molecular Approaches for the Detection of Fungal Phytopathogens*. CRC Press.

Tambo JA, Abdoulaye T., 2012. Climate change and agricultural technology adoption in Nigeria. *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 17(3): 277–292.

Teklewold H, Kassie M, Shiferaw B., 2013. Adoption of multiple sustainable agricultural practices in Ethiopia. *Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 64(3): 597–623.

URT, 2022. Basic Education Statistics in Tanzania. Ministry of Education. <https://www.moe.go.tz/sw/statistics>

Vaidya B, Rana H, Sharma SR., 2023. Adoption of digital agro-advisory services among smallholder farmers. *Bodhi: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 313–345.

Van Campenhout B, Spielman DJ, Lecoutere E, 2021. ICTs to provide agricultural advice to smallholder farmers in Uganda. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 103(1): 317–337.

Wossen T, Abdoulaye T, Alene A, Haile MG, Feleke S, Olanrewaju A, Manyong V., 2017. Impacts of extension access and cooperative membership on technology adoption. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 54: 223–233.

Yamane T., 1973. *Statistics: An Introductory Analysis*. 3rd Edition. Harper and Row, New York, USA.

Zhang Q, Brown PH., 1999. Distribution and transport of foliar applied zinc in pistachio. *Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science*, 124(4): 433–436.